

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN CREATING A MODERN EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Sotbarov Atabek Asilbek ugli

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7967384>

***Abstract.** The article describes the pedagogical factors and conditions of creating a modern educational environment.*

***Keywords:** technology, pedagogy, education, integration, method.*

Currently, in modern educational conditions, teaching methods are experiencing a difficult period related to changing educational goals, developing a new generation state education standard based on a competency-based approach. All these situations require new pedagogical research in the field of teaching methods of subjects, the search for innovative means, forms and methods of teaching and education related to the development and introduction of modern education and information technologies into the educational process. The main goal of secondary vocational education is to train a qualified specialist who is capable of effective professional activity in his specialty and is competitive in the labor market. In the educational process, modern educational technologies are used to improve the quality of education, to make effective use of study time, and to reduce the share of reproductive activity of students in order to realize the cognitive and creative activity of the student. Home work. Modern educational technologies, regardless of age and level of education, are aimed at individualization, distance and variability of the educational process, academic mobility of students.

Educational technology is a systematic way of designing, implementing, evaluating, correcting and then repeating the learning process.

At the developing stage of scientific and technical development, the sharp increase in information and the limitation of time for using it in the teaching process, as well as the requirements for perfect preparation of young people for life, require the introduction of new technologies into the educational system.

In the days when today's technology has developed according to the needs of the times, the teacher's awareness of information technologies requires the ability to use them effectively in accordance with his professional abilities and needs. Critical analysis based on the use of new information technologies, the ability to choose and change the content of education, to feel responsibility for the decisions made, is one of the important qualities of a modern teacher.

The need to "widely introduce new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods into the educational process, curricula and programs of higher education..." is emphasized in many places. This leads to a qualitative renewal of the scientific-educational process and further improvement based on the introduction of modern educational and pedagogical technologies.

With the improvement of science and technology, the limits of human activity are finally expanding, new technologies with great opportunities for teaching in the audience are coming. The changes that are taking place indicate that now the primary process of "learning" does not fit into the scope of traditional methods and teaching tools, and does not correspond to the individual ability of the teacher. It is no secret that the use of information technologies in the educational process expands students' independent thinking and creative thinking. The use of computer

technology in the educational process models the communicative activity of students, expands their creative activity, ensures communication-intervention activity of students in education, and forms the abilities of promptness in tasks and responses. If all pedagogues use their new ideas and pedagogical technologies effectively in creating a modern educational environment, they will facilitate the educational environment and the educational process, including the education of pupils and students, and ensure its quality and efficiency.

Lectures, practical and group trainings, seminars, special trainings, interactive methods of education are carried out through information and communication technologies. This will cause future pedagogues in higher education institutions to use educational methods effectively for use in the educational process. Below we want to mention the styles of educational methods;

1. Micro education (applying educational materials to the production of small parts of sections in a certain sequence) is recommended as an important element of the introductory part of this lesson.

2. Module technology of education.

3. Compilation of knowledge according to the content of the subjects

4. Studying educational texts in parts using advanced tools.

5. Application of business games (labyrinth, problem area, etc.).

6. Programmatic education.

7. Education based on audiovisual course programs created for educational subjects.

8. Organization of pedagogical activity on a scientific basis.

Pedagogical technologies allow the use of educational tools in several directions at the same time. At the same time, the "hardware" system (video books, educational CDs, music albums, etc.) is widely used.

REFERENCES

1. Belozertsev, E.P. Vocational education pedagogy: textbook / E.P. Belozertsev, A.D. Goneev, A.G. Pashkov, ed. V. A. Slastenin, 4th edition, Deleted. - M.: IT Academy, 2008. -- 368 p. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 December 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 12 www.openscience.uz 555
2. Borisova, N.V. Educational technologies as an object of pedagogical choice: textbook. pension / N. V. Borisova. - M.: ITsPKPS, 2000. -- 146 p.
3. J.E. Usarov, L.G. Babkhodjaeva, G.N. Sharipova, N.J. Eshnaev. Pedagogical competence./Study manual. - Chirchik, "Farzay polygraph". 2021.
4. PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF MIXED EDUCATION Khalmatova Dilobod Alimzhanovna attachment=12285 2023 – year
5. Khimmataliyev, D. O., Abdijalilova, S. A., Elmurzaeva, N. K., Turaev, M. F., Allayorova, S. B., & Janbayeva, M. S. (2022). Formation Of A Cluster System In The Sphere Of Education In Uzbekistan: Problems And Prospects. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5634-5638.
6. Oblakulovna, Ernazarova Gulnora. "Application Of The Acmeological Approach To Improve The Efficiency Of The Professional Educational Process." *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results* (2023): 2551-2555.

7. Mukhamedov, G. I., Usarov, J. E., Khimmataliev, D. O., Khodjamkulov, U. N., Ernazarova, G. O., & Rasulov, A. N. (2023). Pedagogical Training the Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of the Innovation Cluster. *Telematique*, 22(01), 29-31.
8. Rakhmanova, M., and M. Meylieva. "Socio-Psychological Features of the Formation of a System of Attitudes to Career Choice in Adolescents." *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 2.12 (2021): 4-7.
9. Musurmanova, A., Ismailova, Z., Fayzullaev, R., Rakhmonova, M., & Sharifbaeva, H. (2022). Echnologies For The Development Of Technical Competence Of Students On The Basis Of Innovative And Integrated Approaches. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 1631-1637.
10. Mirzaahmadovna M. S. LEARNING OBJECTIVES OF DUAL HIGHER EDUCATION STUDY //Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 192-195.
11. Omonovich K. D., Mirzaahmadovna M. S. The Relevance of the Dual Learning Model for Our Country //Telematique. – 2023. – T. 22. – №. 01. – C. 265–274-265–274.
12. Djanbaeva, M. S., & Allayorova, S. B. (2021). AMALIYOTCHI PSIXOLOG SHAXS VA MUTAXASSIS SIFATIDA. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(Special Issue 1), 390-394.
13. Qorayev, S. B., & Allayorova, S. B. (2021). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini pirls xalqaro baholash dasturi tizimiga tayyorlash jarayonini takomillashtirish masalalari. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 443-448.
14. Mirzotilloeyvna, Radjabova Zuhra, and S. R. Mirzayeva. "Psychological factors of adolescence and teacher cooperation in choosing a profession." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.5 (2021): 834-842.
15. Mirzotillaevna, Radbajabova Zukhra. "Intelligence as a psychological problem." *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research* 11.10 (2022): 79-82.
16. Musurmonov, R., Eshmanova, N., Satbarov, A., & Elmurzaeva, N. (2021). Innovative Activity In Education-The Requirement Of The Period. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(02), 2021.
17. Barakaevich, Qoraev Samaridin, and Sotbarov Atabek Asilbek Ogli. "Requirements for Preparing Vocational Education Teachers in the Innovation Cluster of Higher Education." *JournalNX*: 952-955.
18. Khimmataliev, D. O., Elmurzayeva, N. K., Sharakhmatova, A. K., Sotbarov, A. A., Khalmatova, D. A., & Jamoldinova, S. N. (2022). Development Of The Pedagogical (Educational) Cluster In The Regional Educational Space. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5629-5633.
19. Alimjanovna, Khalmatova Dilobad. "The role and significance of volunteers in the process of formation of ecological culture." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 12.4 (2022): 108-111.
20. Khalmatova, D. A. (2021). Formation of ecological culture in students in the process of extracurricular activities on the example of grades (9-11). In *Актуальные Вопросы Современной Науки И Образования* (pp. 201-203).